

Inheritance study of nodal rooting in deepwater rice

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Deepwater rice varieties are characterized by their ability to elongate under excess water. Besides elongation ability, these varieties possess nodal roots, nodal tillers, and kneeing ability, among others. Nodal roots are needed by deepwater rice because, under conditions of excess water, basal roots rot and plants float on the water surface. Nodal roots keep the plants buoyant and facilitate the uptake of water-soluble nutrients (Khan et al 1982, Boonwite 1979). Boonwite (1979) found an insignificant but positive correlation between elongation ability and nodal rooting. Tripathy and Balakrishna Rao (1985) also studied the inheritance of characters including nodal rooting that are associated with the floating habit.

We studied the inheritance of nodal rooting in eight crosses of rice in the 1995 wet season (WS) at CRRI, Cuttack. Two deepwater rice varieties, Jalamagna and TCA4 (tall, elongating types), capable of producing nodal roots under deepwater conditions, were crossed with three tall, nonelongating varieties, Khao Y Khao, Mtu-6, and Kwan-Fu-1, during the 1994 WS.

Seeds of the parents, their F_1 , and F_2 were sown in big galvanized iron trays (60 × 60 cm). Forty-two-day-old seedlings were placed in 60-cm-deep water in a cemented deepwater tank. After 30 d, the water was drained and plants were observed for nodal rooting. Ten plants of each parent and F_1 and about 200–300 plants of each F_2 were observed for nodal rooting.

All plants of parents Jalamagna and TCA4 had nodal roots, whereas those of Khao Y Khao, Kwan-Fu-1, and Mtu-6 had none (see table). All F_1 plants of crosses involving Jalamagna or TCA4 had nodal roots, indicating dominance of the trait. The F_2 plants of these crosses segregated into nine with nodal rooting to seven without nodal rooting, implying that two dominant complementary genes control nodal rooting. The F_1 and F_2 plants of the crosses between TCA4 and Jalamagna (deepwater varieties) had nodal rooting, whereas those between Khao Y Khao and Mtu-6 (nondeepwater varieties) did not.

The data show the presence of two dominant complementary genes for nodal rooting in rice. Nodal rooting occurs when

both genes are present. The absence of either or both genes results in plants with no nodal roots as in nonelongating rice varieties.

References

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Nodal rooting behavior of F_1 and F_2 , 1995 wet season, CRRI, Cuttack.

Cross	F_1			F_2			χ^2 (9:7)	P value
	Observed frequency			Observed frequency				
	Plants tested (no.)	With nodal rooting	Without nodal rooting	Plants tested (no.)	With nodal rooting	Without nodal rooting		
Khao Y Khao/Jalamagna ^a	10	10	0	290	150	140	2.414 ns	0.25–0.10
Khao Y Khao/TCA4 ^a	10	10	0	268	146	122	0.342 ns	0.75–0.50
Kwan-Fu-1/Jalamagna	10	10	0	300	175	125	0.529 ns	0.50–0.25
Kwan-Fu-1/TCA4	10	10	0	300	185	115	3.576 ns	0.10–0.05
Mtu-6/Jalamagna	10	10	0	287	152	135	1.261 ns	0.50–0.25
Mtu-6/TCA4	10	10	0	185	100	85	0.362 ns	0.75–0.50
TCA4/Jalamagna	10	10	0	202	202	0	–	–
Khao Y Khao/Mtu-6	10	10	10	275	0	275	–	–

^aBoth Jalamagna and TCA4 had nodal roots in all 10 plants. Nodal roots were absent in Khao Y Khao, Kwan-Fu-1, and Mtu-6. ns = not significant.